

Mini Thesis Report

Evaluating the Impact and Challenges of Campus Sustainability Initiatives at Noakhali Science and Technology University

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ABSTRACT

This paper critically reviews the results and challenges encountered during the implementation of campus sustainability programs in NSTU, and is presented as an attempt to understand how sustainable practices can be implemented in universities worldwide. The study addresses a significant research gap by critically analyzing the particular challenges that are faced by NSTU, assessment of stakeholders' awareness and recommending context-specific solutions. Unlike most of the sustainability research, this study indicates that initiatives should be localized to university settings in Bangladesh unlike focusing mainly on western institutions.

The aim is to provide insights that may improve sustainability programs and future SP in higher education. This study had two specific objectives: one was focus well-informed of stakeholders at NSTU are on the CS initiatives and exploring barriers which were faced by NSTU in implementing these initiatives.

These important findings emphasize the need for specific awareness campaigns and integrating sustainability in the academic curriculum through providing an overview of the levels of awareness among different stakeholders. The government has to intervene and allow NSTU to fund its activities within scarce resources. Thus, overcoming constraints on resources, maintaining involvement of stakeholders, and creating sustainable strategies adapted to the local context.

In terms of social problems that affect other universities that have a similar problem regarding SP, the new framework is beneficial. Conclusion and recommendations provide NSTU with a map for negotiating through a complex journey of campus sustainability ensuring equitable mix of biological, social and financial elements in higher education.

Keywords: Campus Sustainability, Sustainability Initiatives, Sustainability Practices, Sustainability Challenges

LIST OF ABBREVIATION

CS= Campus Sustainability

HEI's= Higher Education Institute Society (HEIS)

NSTU= Noakhali Science and Technology University

SI= Sustainability Initiatives

SP= Sustainable Practices

SA= Sustainability Awareness

SB= Sustainability Behaviour

STARS= The Sustainability Tracking, Assessment and Rating System

ULAB= University of Liberal Arts Bangladesh

GLOSSARY

Term	Definition
Sustainability	The ability to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.
Campus Sustainability	The practice of operating and maintaining a Universities or university in an environmentally, socially, and economically responsible manner.
Green Building	The design, construction, and operation of buildings in an environmentally responsible and resource-efficient way.
Renewable Energy	Energy derived from sources that are naturally replenished, such as sunlight, wind, and rain.
Carbon Footprint	The total amount of greenhouse gases, primarily carbon dioxide that are emitted directly or indirectly by an individual, organization, event, or product.
Energy Efficiency	The use of less energy to perform the same task, reducing energy waste and environmental impact.
Waste Reduction	Minimizing the generation of waste and promoting the reuse, recycling, and composting of materials.
Biodiversity	The variety of life in a particular habitat, ecosystem, or on Earth as a whole, including the variety of species, genetic differences within species, and ecosystems.
Green Transportation	Modes of transportation that have a lower environmental impact, such as walking, cycling, electric vehicles, and public transit.

Sustainable Procurement	The practice of purchasing goods and services that have a reduced environmental and social impact throughout their life cycle.
Water Conservation	The efficient use and management of water resources to reduce water consumption and waste.
Climate Action Plan	A strategic framework that outlines specific measures and goals to mitigate and adapt to climate change within a specific timeframe.
Triple Bottom Line	It is a framework that considers the financial, environmental and social implications of organizations' behaviour as they aim at having equilibrium between profit, people and planet.
Environmental Justice	No discrimination in any matter relating to the environment is racial or ethnic origin but justice and equity must be observed by all.
Community Engagement	Decision-making processes regarding sustainability initiatives should engage campus communities and their surrounding areas.
Eco-Friendly Practices	Practices that promote a secure, resilient and environmentally responsible food system, including local and sustainable sourcing.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Noakhali Science and Technology University (NSTU), is a dedicated to achieving in educational excellence and environmental conservation. However, over the past few years, higher education institutions worldwide including NSTU authority have begun to awaken to the significance of integrating sustainability on their campuses. It is worth noting that such undertakings are important because they are associated with global issues such as conservation of environment, social responsibility as well as economic sustenance of the planet (Altassan, 2023).

Universities are instrumental in the shaping of future leaders and professionals who understand the challenges posed by climate change and resource scarcity. These institutions create a sense of responsibility among their students, teachers, and employers by encouraging them to participate in sustainable projects (Leal Filho et al., 2019).

However, in order for sustainability programs to succeed in higher education institutes like NSTU an understanding about various aspects such as stakeholder's awareness and challenges must be understood. Importantly, it is necessary to examine stakeholders' awareness at NSTU regarding how willingly engaged they are in these initiatives (Kutsyuruba, 2016).

In addition, the challenges NSTU faced in implementing different sustainability strategies can be learned by looking at the obstacles. Lack of enough finance is one of these problems or lack of resources or resistance within an institution (Ullah et al., 2021). It is therefore important for the stakeholder awareness on sustainability issues on how they lead to challenges facing NSTU as far as sustainability implementation is concerned. This study aims to provide significant insights that can enhance the effectiveness of sustainability programs at NSTU. It can further be used as a guide to other learning institutions interested in embracing SP in higher education.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Though this should not mean that evaluation should not be done concerning the problems faced by such institutions while trying to engage in sustainable activities here and there, globally it has become necessary for all higher education establishments around the world including NSTU but also other regions particularly this place to focus on these areas with a view to improving their efficient working conditions. NSTU is committed towards implementing sustainability into its strategic goals.

There is still an unclear understanding of the levels of stakeholder awareness and barriers inhibiting the effectiveness of these programs despite NSTU's commitment to sustainability as revealed by this study.

The major problem here is that there has been no, or little, inquiry into the levels of stakeholder awareness concerning NSTU's sustainability activities. In order for an evaluation of sustainability practices to be effective, they must become a part of university life and stakeholders such as faculty members, students, local residents, and administrative staff should know how much they are involved and know. (Ferrero-Ferrero et al., 2018).

It is also important to uncover and examine other obstacles that hinder proper implementation and continuity in regards to sustainable development at NSTU. According to previous studies, higher education institutions face numerous complex issues which manifest in terms of financial limitations, lack of enough basic infrastructure facilities, resistance to change and policy gaps (Govindan et al., 2021). It is crucial for them to understand the specific challenges encountered in designing effective solutions for their management and control.

As a result, NSTU does not advance SP due to lack of an in-depth assessment of stakeholder awareness and comprehensive analysis of barriers. It is also possible to overcome some of these limitations by carrying out an empirical research and analysis with regard to sustainability programs at NSIT. This study will be important for other institutions that are concerned with sustainability in education.

1.3 Research Objective

The primary objective is to provide relevant information that could enhance the efficiency of the sustainable initiatives and help guide SP in future for higher education.

1.3.1 Specific Objectives

This research will be guided by the following specific objectives:

1. To investigate what extent the NSTU stakeholders are conscious about their campus sustainability initiative.
2. To explore the challenges of the NSTU sustainability initiative.
3. To identify and assess the current sustainable practices implemented by NSTU stakeholders, with a focus on understanding their effectiveness, impact, and areas for improvement.

1.4 Scope of the Study

The aim of this study is to assess implications and challenges within the sustainability programs at NSTU. The study seeks to identify awareness and understanding about sustainability initiatives within the university, as well as obstacles preventing effective and sustainable implementation of these initiatives. The study will look at how the sustainability programs done by NSTU are viewed by stakeholders such as students, faculty, staffs and communities. The study will use questionnaires, survey question and open ended question to determine the level of awareness and engagement among stakeholders in sustainable programs (Alsaati et al., 2020).

Moreover, this study investigates barriers against sustainability faced by NSTU. For instance, there are financial limitations, physical limitations, institutional resistance and policy inadequacies that make it difficult to carry out sustainable practices successfully and continuously (Stupak et al., 2021).

However, this research has its own limitations. This research may not be able to capture all the important elements of sustainability projects in NSTU because time and resources were limited. First of all in this study the researcher wants to know what stakeholders think about SP, what main challenges they face and how stakeholder aware their SP.

The findings from the research could strengthen NSTU's sustainability initiatives. Furthermore these findings might be used as benchmarks for other higher learning institutions that wish to build their sustainability programs.

1.5 Rationale of the Study

This research is meant to delve into the efficiency and limitations of sustainability programs at NSTU. Thus, it is essential to cultivate a culture of sustainability in universities such as NSTU. However, there are no comprehensive reviews on stakeholders' knowledge levels and their challenges (Veisi et al., 2022).

It is important to comprehend the levels of awareness as well as involvement by NSTU stakeholders in relation to sustainable development initiatives. Additionally, limited understanding of this area does not allow assessing current sustainability efforts' ratings in terms of their potentials to breed green habits and behaviors amongst university population (Mccowan et al., 2021).

Moreover, given that institutions of learning have acknowledged sustainability as a fundamental principle for their existence, it is vital to critically examine these challenges impeding their continued being. Like many other higher education establishments across the world, NSTU presumably faces complex obstacles that make integration of sustainable practices impossible in its system. Knowing these problems may guide NSTU towards removing barriers (Amin et al, 2023).

It is critical that this research be conducted as it may come up with useful findings and recommendations to assist NSTU sustainability efforts. In order to preserve the environment and maintain social responsibilities, these findings can be a turning point for other similar universities' sustainability policies.

The study's goal is to fill gaps in existing literature and provide empirical data that will advance knowledge on SP in universities.

1.6 Conclusion

This study aims at evaluating stakeholder understanding levels of sustainability projects at NSTU along with the barriers towards their implementation. Moreover, the study targets identifying awareness levels among NSTU stakeholders and problems associated with implementation of sustainability projects. The study will encompass perceptions, attitudes, and issues which could foster a sustainable NSTU. This objective is intended to improve the current contents and offer solutions to institutions like NSTU. It also seeks to contribute to the wider conversation about SP in higher education by focusing on environmental sustainability and social responsibility.

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CHAPTER TWO
LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The importance of sustainability efforts in universities is that they address global ecological challenges and nurture socially responsible future leaders and professionals (Kuo et al., 2022; Leal Filho et al, 2022). Integrating sustainability values into the operations and ethos of educational institutions aims at creating environmentally-conscious and socially accountable citizens that can bring about positive changes in today's fast-transforming global conditions. (Rodríguez et al., 2020).

The term sustainable development was first used in the *Sustainable Development*, 1987 Brundtland Report which defined it as “a process which meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs.” This broad approach recognized that social well-being is linked to environmental protection. Sustainability requires striking a balance between safeguarding nature, ensuring social justice and promoting economic growth for real sustainability (Mensah, 2019).

CS engages in activities that enhance the life expectancy of planet earth. This means that it is an act of goodwill toward people, environment and economy because all these three elements are involved.

Sometimes universities undergo massive transformations while implementing such programs successful. However, these benefits include reduced energy and water usage, less pollution and increased environmental awareness among students. This approach is discussed by (Kamal et al., 2019).

What are the effects of striving for sustainability at higher education institutions? In terms of waste, they strive to reduce them through their recycling activities. Some firms have started adopting alternative sources of energy like electricity in order to combat pollutions (Omer, 2009). Yet, these efforts face challenges sometimes. There are numerous challenges that campuses face in addressing issues on campus. They range from restrictions, calling for help from authorities and ensuring wide acceptance of these changes (Fazey et al., 2021).

For this reason, Universities have to teach safety together with treating people equally well and being responsible with money (Barth & Rieckmann, 2012).

Why do universities consider sustainability as a vital issue? Demonstrating leadership is what it is all about. Inculcate the idea in stakeholder's minds that they should manage their earth responsibly.

The institutions exhibit their concern for environment through practices of sustainability. Energy and resource conservation can also save universities costs (Leal Filho et al., 2015).

Sustainability initiatives on most campuses can be built around various areas. One other possible way is to include other non-fossil energy into the system such as biofuels. (Mazzoleni, 2022). This should mean that it has to be part of every subject so that every person can take part in finding answers to the questions. (Lambrechts et al., 2013).

Even though there are several challenges related to CS projects, they are well known for their value and effectiveness in education. The work by Lozano et al. (2015) analyses how universities may help in raising awareness about sustainable development among students and staff without being intrusive. This research conducted by Lozano et al. (2015) shows that it adds to preservation but also helps people feel responsible.

It is important to mention that a number of scholars have addressed the issue of campuses' sustainability initiatives. For example, Wu et al., (2021) have shown how energy-saving programs have reduced greenhouse gas emissions significantly. According to Sánchez-Hernández and Maldonado-Briegas (2019), universities can also become agents for promotion of socially responsible behavior.

Nevertheless, some obstacles face CS initiatives; Bell et al. (2022) argue that leadership commitment and stakeholder involvement are needed to overcome resistance to change. Similarly, Villena and Gioia (2018) Constraints, unfamiliarity with sustainable practices and lack of cooperation towards sustainability were among the findings of the study.

The study looks into the effectiveness of NSTU's sustainability undertakings regarding stakeholder participation, challenges experienced as well as context related factors influencing its implementation. The aim of this study is to give important ideas about knowledge on stakeholders about sustainability especially the barriers which are hindering NSTU's sustainability programs as contextual elements influence them. These insights are from recent theoretical writings as well as empirical studies. The involvement of stakeholders is essential

for sustainability projects in schools to succeed (Huang et al., 2021). To understand the impact of NSTU's sustainability programs, there must be transparency about how much different stakeholders such as students, faculty, administration and the local community get involved. (Fernández et al., n.d.)

Besides, obstacles generally impede a smooth implementation and progression of sustainability in academic institutions (Leal Filho et al., 2019). NSTU's sustainability initiatives may face substantial obstacles due to financial constraints, lack of institutional support and cultural resistance. To propose ways on how these issues can be surmounted or a better atmosphere for environmental conservation established demands a careful examination of these challenges.

Additionally, we ought to identify the environmental factors that influence sustainable activities at NSTU. The specific socio-cultural, economic, and environmental contexts within which NSTU operates significantly inform its sustainability plans' structure and functionality (Neshcheret et al., 2023). Understanding these contextual variations will enable suitable and effective sustainable strategies to be formulated for NSTU's particular context.

The main objective of this literature review therefore is to consolidate the existing body of knowledge and provide a comprehensive understanding of the state of sustainability at NSTU. This study aims to shed light on any issues faced and contextual factors, which can guide further actions, towards improving effectiveness of sustainability within the institution through stakeholder input.

In response to global concerns on environmental conservation and responsible management of resources, there has been an increasing focus on sustainability activities in educational institutions (Uddin, 2023). In different regions of the world universities are turning their campuses into laboratories for implementing SP. Rather than just reducing their ecological footprints, they encourage all involved parties to embrace sustainable living practices. (Anuradha et al., 2023).

2.2.1 CS Initiatives in Higher Education

Sustainability programs in higher education institutions are necessary for environmental stewardship, social responsibility, and economic efficiency. The aspiration for sustainability at NSTU is aligned with present days' global sustainability movement embraced by higher education institutions (Pramono Sari et al., 2023).

These programs one major component that requires engagement of stakeholders and fostering awareness. For Krizek et al. (2012), the success of any sustainability program in any higher learning institution largely depends on how much stakeholders are aware about it and have actively participated in it.

For example, different groups such as students, staffs and host communities have to be part of all sustainable projects for schools. It is imperative that there should be good understanding on stakeholder's awareness & involvement regarding sustainability initiatives at NSTU in order to enhance the effectiveness of such initiatives.

However, always many barriers tend to interfere with a smooth progress or implementation of sustainability measures within the university. According to Leal Filho et al. (2022) tertiary institutions face diverse obstacles when dealing with sustainability due to its complex nature.

It also has to do with the contextual nature of such problems and therefore calls for a tailor-made methodology in handling them. According to Kioupi and Voulvoulis (2019) any educational institution, including NSTU, operates in specific socio-cultural, economic and ecological context which determine the acceptance and implementation of sustainability measures. Consequently, it is necessary to extensively research on these contextual aspects so as to have proper means that can help overcome hurdles towards sustainable development (Mensah, 2019).

2.2.2 Stakeholder Engagement and Consciousness

For any sustainability initiative for education institutions to succeed there must be stakeholder participation. To be successful sustainability programs in educational institutions should involve stakeholders. The way through which these stakeholders are engaged especially through effective methods can impact on their understanding and participation deeply.

The way stakeholders are involved, especially through efficient means, can completely affect the level of understanding and participation.

Chakraborty et al. (2019) assert that communication and engagement are key to sustainability in higher education. Stakeholder engagement via educational programs, workshops, and decision-making process will foster a sense of ownership and a desire for sustainability according to Chakraborty et al. (2019).

Student involvement is another important factor that García-González et al. (2019) found supported it in their study about fostering student sustainability. Nonetheless, students like other significant actors could be useful in shaping policies or SP at the institutional levels hence Universities community behavior transformation (Gonzalez et al., 2021).

2.2.3 Challenges Faced by NSTU Sustainability Initiatives

NSTU faces several challenges while trying to adopt sustainability programs. Many times financial limitation remains a big problem. The main challenge associated with supporting sustainability at the higher education institutional level is lack of sufficient financial resources (Leal Filho et al., 2018). Other alternatives for funding should be explored or the available money used optimally.

Furthermore, nurturing sustainable activities within this institution's culture and leadership is critical. In doing so, NSTU will establish itself as a leading institution in terms of sustainability while ensuring its success.

2.2.4 Contextual Factors Shaping Sustainability Initiatives at NSTU

Various sustainability initiatives in NSTU have been influenced by several context-specific factors. These case Wu et al. (2021) emphasized on recognizing such attributes and coming up with appropriate sustainability solutions that match those contexts (Wu et al., 2021). An analysis of the NSTU context helps understand issues concerning sustainable development from a social, cultural, economic and environmental standpoint. It will assist in finding practical solutions that can work for specific situations.

2.2.5 Sustainability initiatives in higher education case studies

Most of these cases explain how higher education institutions can incorporate ideas of sustainability into their practices with success. Some universities have made progress by marrying the curriculum with green or sustainability initiatives led by students or through investment in energy-saving technologies (Mccowan et al., 2021). The studies in these-case are essential and they bring valuable lessons for the NSTU adaptation.

2.2.6 Frameworks for Assessing CS

One such tool is the sustainability tracking, assessment, and rating system (STARS) that provides systematic approaches on assessing how sustainable initiatives affect higher education institutions (N.D-A). The application of such frameworks by NSTU will be helpful in streamlining the performance evaluation process and determining areas that need improvement.

2.2.7 Sustainability Practices

SP must be adopted for CS courses to reach more students. This study aims to discuss implementation of SP strategy in higher education facilities as well as how sustainability can be integrated into daily activities (Angelaki et al., 2023). In this study Leal Angelaki et al. (2023), several strategies including waste minimization, energy saving plans and eco-friendly transport are put in place.

2.2.8 Sustainability Challenges

Obstacles often stand in the way of these sustainable programs in educational settings. Lack of finance, barriers set up by institutions as well as opposition to cultural change may hinder success. Such problems have been addressed by Ávila et al. (2017) for example concerning SP implementation at tertiary level.

2.2.9 Sustainability Reporting

Measuring the impacts of sustainability initiatives is why sustainability reporting is crucial. Sari et al. (2023) argue that higher education institutions need strong and reliable systems for reporting. Furthermore, transparent reporting assists in benchmarking and accountability through sustainability components of the environment, society and economy (n.d.-b).

2.2.10 Incentives for Sustainable Behavior

Besides, incentives are a significant driver of sustainable behavior in stakeholders. Zhou et al., (2021) hold that there are various ways of promoting sustainable behaviors among which incentives are one. By implementing rewarding systems, recognition programs and integrating sustainability into grading standards, the stakeholders can be encouraged to participate actively in lifelong learning activities like research projects (Zhou et al., 2021).

2.2.11 Suggestions and Comments

As per Yue et al. (2019), an organization must involve people who are concerned about a specific issue. Therefore, creating transparent communication channels that allow views from students, faculty or nonacademic staff on how they perceive different school's sustainability activities could turn to greater advantage. In this way, ownership principles as well as participation become part of decision-making processes (Yue et al., 2019).

2.2.12 Future Directions and Recommendations:

Researchers propose different measures towards improving sustainability endeavors Rodríguez et al., (2020) suggest that universities should infuse sustainability into all academic programs, promote interdisciplinary collaboration, and establish relevant centers or institutes on sustainability. These developments will stimulate innovation and lay the ground for sustainable development in NSTU.

2.3 Research gap

However, few studies have been done to highlight the challenges higher education in worldwide with regards to sustainability, there are no worked for NSTU sustainability initiative before. Not only NSTU but also Bangladeshi Higher education institutes work a little for encompassing sustainability, some studies found focusing on Sustainability in Bangladesh, one study of Shamsuddoha et al. 2012, focused the role, coverage, ways, importance, present status and other relevant issues of sustainability in higher education of Bangladesh

Another studies found from Bangladeshi higher education institution ULLAB conducted a research focusing on campus SB and SP (Bhowmik et al., 2017), which focusing environmental and stakeholder behaviour at all along with university sustainability policy. Another study of sustainability focusing on ES attitudes in three different HEIs in Bangladesh based on student perception, and stakeholder's awareness and targeted approaches (Haque et al., 2023).

NSTU's sustainability initiatives have not been thoroughly researched, despite these important contributions. NSTU's specific challenges and opportunities within its local context have not been studied yet. This research aims to address this gap by conducting a thorough examination of the sustainability landscape at NSTU, taking into account the institution's limited resources, government regulations, and cultural influences, including religious aspects.

2.4 NSTU Sustainability Initiative

Noakhali Science and Technology University (NSTU), with its focus on To engage in partnerships with local and global communities, government agencies, industries and universities aspiring for sustainable society and economy, has a natural responsibility to

promote sustainable practices. Here are some potential initiatives NSTU could undertake to lead the way in sustainability-

2.4.1. Greening the Campus

Encourage students and faculty to use bicycles which are other greener means of transport.

Conduct energy audits to identify areas for improvement, retrofit buildings with energy-efficient lighting and appliances, and implement smart energy management systems.

Implement a comprehensive waste management system that includes composting, recycling, and responsible disposal of e-waste. Encourage students and faculty to reduce their waste generation through awareness campaigns and eco-friendly alternatives.

Develop green spaces on campus that include gardens for better air quality, more biodiversity, and improved well-being for the campus community as a whole.

2.4.2. Sustainable Education and Research

Integrate sustainability concepts into existing courses across all disciplines. Develop new courses and programs focused on environmental science, renewable energy, green technology, and sustainable development.

Encourage research on topics related to sustainable solutions for local and regional challenges such as climate change adaptation, water resource management, sustainable agriculture conducted on some department like Environmental Science and disaster Management (ESDM), FIMS, Agriculture and other department.

In order to conduct researches about the environment and human life, work with local communities and organizations in which you will also get an opportunity to organize seminars and campaigns. Empower the entire community through provision of knowledge and skills on how to practice sustainable development.

2.4.3. Operational Excellence

Implementing green procurement practices is one way through which you can enhance sustainability within your business. Some of these include purchasing recycled materials, energy efficient products and locally sourced goods.

Landscaping, buildings, and irrigation systems should have water saving measures. Conduct

educational campaigns on water conservation awareness.

Faculty members as well as learners should embrace sustainable transport services such as bicycles or public transport means like buses available within campus premises.

2.4.4. Fostering a Culture of Sustainability

Students' clubs for sustainability should take precedence over any other group since they can easily organize events promoting ecological conservation. These groups can be given money by universities so that they invest it into programs aimed at environmental protection.

How would administrators award lecturers, school workers plus scholars who have tried their best in ensuring that institutions are ecofriendly?

There is need for a comprehensive communication strategy to engage all stakeholders regarding sustainability initiatives in the institution. Engaging the whole university community requires a well-developed communication campaign strategy.

They are just a few ideas that NSTU can do. NSTU can become a leader in sustainable education, research, and practices if it takes sustainable development as a whole and involves all members of the university community in decision-making processes to set an example for other universities and have positive effect on the environment.

2.4 Conclusion

The holistic assessment of sustainability activities at Noakhali Science & Technology University (NSTU) indicates how complex and diverse it could be to promote sustainability practices in higher education institutions. Based on an analysis of stakeholder interactions, challenges faced, contextual issues as well as effective methods used in sustainability programs; we can draw certain valuable conclusions and recommendations.

The importance of involving stakeholders has been seen as a vital element in achieving sustainability plans. Sustainability is enhanced through effective communication, educational programs and engagement in decision making by various stakeholders. To promote sustainability projects, advocate for change and encourage behavioral change among the campus community, it may be important to engage students.

To sum up, this comprehensive assessment gives valuable perspectives and recommendations for NSTU to develop sustainability. Thus, this examines stakeholder involvement, barriers,

contextual factors, best practices and future directions for sustainability programs within the institution with view of enhancing them as well as creating an environmentally responsible and socially conscious stakeholder society in the process.

03

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This study is about what makes Noakhali Science and Technology University so different from other universities around the world when it comes to incorporating principles of sustainability into higher education. Sustainable Education is the measure of the level of consciousness and involvement on sustainability associated with challenges.

Quantitative research is suitable for this type of research because researcher could look at relationships between variables that exist within a specific context.

Within sustainability studies, stakeholder awareness, and participation are measured and often evaluated with the help of various quantitative tools or methods. For example, Wiek et al. (2011) reveal that most often empirical evidence about the effectiveness of sustainability interventions has been derived from quantitative research. This is particularly relevant to any work which evaluates how successful NSTU's efforts to make it more sustainable have been. Quantitative research methods are widely used in the social sciences to examine attitudes, behaviors, and perceptions. According to (Creswell & Creswell, 2018), quantitative research is suitable for investigating stakeholder awareness as well as other issues around sustainability.

3.2 Research Design

Researcher use a quantitative research design in order to get data and analyze it in a more organized way. It is the cross-sectional nature study, which means that it can be used to look at stakeholders' views at one time only. This design further simplifies statistical analysis that can be conducted to better understand the present sustainability practices and awareness within NSTU. This study follows a quantitative-methods design that combines techniques for quantifying different aspects related to participation, awareness, and issues concerning sustainability by NSTU stakeholders. Quantitative research insights are gathered through structured survey questionnaire using Likert-scale questions and convenient sampling via Google Forms.

In these survey question one part was open-ended questions which were analysed thematically with an aim of identifying trends and original findings. Correlation analysis among others are some of the ways through which quantitative data was analysed using IBM SPSS software. These findings, when coded thematically are cross-sectional study. Rigor is assured through triangulation, member verification and peer review procedures. The research was divided into stages; creating the questionnaire, pre-testing phase, data gathering, analysing data and report

writing stage. The timeframe is reasonable and in line with the availability of stakeholders and academic restrictions.

3.3 Study Area

The research will be limited to the higher education institution in Bangladesh, which is NSTU. The range of activities undertaken by NSTU shows that it is committed to sustainability, thus making it a suitable place for investigating complexities related to stakeholder engagement and SP implementation challenges.

Noakhali Science and Technology University (NSTU) in Bangladesh serves as the focus of this study, being unique within its own location's circumstances. The study concentrates on the main campus itself, where there is exclusive architecture and amenities that provide insights into sustainability practices and experiences. Central among these are administrative offices representing different disciplines and management philosophies. This study also recognizes the area beyond school boundaries since it is influenced by local communities when it comes to sustainable programs. For purposes of research and academic pursuit, a university like NSTU is relevant considering its emphasis on sustainability as well as the global connections. Consequently, selection was based on unique features of NSTU for an in-depth examination of stakeholder consciousness and obstacles related to sustainability. Nevertheless, drawbacks include the need for complete data availability and the possibility of non-generalizability to other institutions. The study's ramifications go beyond that; it offers insightful information for improving sustainability practices at NSTU and acts as a resource for international conversations about sustainability integration in higher education.

3.4 Population

Among the broad and encompassing population under consideration are, academics, administrative personnel, students as well as NSTU-affiliated communities. Through this intentional inclusivity in ensuring diverse range of viewpoints, university sustainability programs can be perceived holistically.

The scope of this study involves several Noakhali Science and Technology University (NSTU) affiliated stakeholders.

3.4.1 This comprises:

Students: Enrolled from different batches in distinct academic programs.

Faculty Members: Representing a range of academic subjects and departments.

Staffs: All those who assist with NSTU's administrative operations are included in this category.

3.5 Sample and Sampling Technique

This research examines Noakhali Science and Technology University (NSTU) associated groups' populations.

The study applies Convenient Sampling to select individuals from different strata of NSTU. A tailored Google Form survey is administered to students and faculty members picked conveniently following which it is distributed through social media, direct messaging platforms as well as community forums. To ensure a representative sample that is broad based, targeted outreach includes administrative staff and local communities

Students: 86 students from different departments at NSTU will be chosen at Convenient for the sample.

Faculty: 05 Faculty selected at Convenient from various faculty departments.

Staffs: 05 staffs chosen at Convenient who work in trash management and tree planting.

3.5.1 Procedure

There are several stages in conveniently selecting the faculty and students. First of all, I select all department in NSTU, then I provide my survey questionnaire among all of that group. Participation is open for faculties or students within the selected departments conveniently.

3.5.2 Justification

The method ensures that every faculty member or student has an equal chance of being included therefore providing a more accurate and comprehensive portrayal of the academic community at NSTU.

3.5.3 Recruitment and Participation

Some of the techniques used in recruiting are personalized invites through social media, direct messaging and community forums. The focus is to ensure that it is clearly communicated that involvement in voluntary and stakeholders' viewpoint matter.

3.6 Data collection Tools

The survey instrument is an exhaustive tool crafted with care to explore NSTU's stakeholders' engagement, sustainability awareness and issues. The survey which has been created on Google

Forms for easy distribution is a combination of open-ended questions as well as Likert scale based questions that fall under various categories.

Demographic information is collected to determine patterns among different groups as well as provide context for answers. Amongst the Likert scale questions, there are also those seeking to evaluate their understanding concerning some programs hence focusing on their awareness about sustainability while some are open-ended. For evaluation of participation in sustainability initiatives, both quantitative and open ended question are applied. By requesting non-participants to explain why they do not participate potential barriers can be identified. A multiple-choice question is used to examine communication channels through which information can be disseminated effectively, this question adopted from (Sustainability awareness survey 2019, N.D).

Likert-scale questions are used to quantify sustainability activities, providing a more detailed picture of participants' behavioral patterns. Quantitative methods are used to measure knowledge of SP, and Likert-scale questions are used to evaluate how effective NSTU's activities are perceived. Stakeholder participation in training or workshops is assessed both quantitatively and open-ended, and they indicate interest in future sustainability-related initiatives. The frequency of reading or gaining access to sustainability reports is examined, as well as the awareness of these reports. The sustainability effectiveness and sustainability practices questionnaire adopted from (Sustainability awareness survey 2019, N.D; Kioupi & Voulvoulis, 2019).

Quantitative analysis is used to identify potential incentives for sustainable behavior, insights added for context. Participants discuss the top three sustainability concerns from their points of view and offer ideas for how to get more people involved. A last open-ended question seeks feedback from all interested parties on NSTU's sustainability programs in order to get a variety of perspectives and possible directions for development. This tools Idea from (Hasan et al., 2023)

Before the survey is distributed, it is put through a thorough pre-testing process with a small number of participants to improve the clarity of the questions, reduce biases, and guarantee the validity and reliability of the data that is gathered.

3.7 Data Collection Process

The procedure for data collection is carefully planned so that participant privacy is guarded and their confidentiality kept intact. This is further reinforced by the comprehensive consent letter stating the purpose of the research and obtaining informed consent. Google Form survey

is designed transparently to ensure that personal identifiers are not included in it. A complete mixture of Likert-scale and open-ended questions, which are embedded into the survey formulation at the preparatory stage, are used to gather stakeholder opinions on sustainability awareness, involvement, issues, and suggestions.

During a rigorous pre-testing phase with a small group feedbacks are obtained to improve this surveys' general usability, relevancy, and clarity. Permission letter as well includes information on informed consent, confidentiality, participant rights besides giving a detailed overview of the study's goals and voluntary nature of participation. During the survey distribution phase, instructors and students are selected at Convenient, and administrative personnel and members of the local community are specifically invited to participate in order to ensure a diverse representation.

To ensure awareness among a wide range of stakeholders, survey links are deliberately posted on NSTU-related forums and communities on social media sites like Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. Stakeholders receive links to the survey and personalized invites via direct message, which increases the probability of participation. Participating in pertinent forums and community places guarantees outreach outside of the academic realm.

The survey is disseminated throughout a predetermined time frame, taking into account both the practical factors of stakeholder availability and the requirement for a significant number of responses. Periodic reminders are issued via a variety of methods to encourage participation and raise response rates, guaranteeing a representative and diverse sample.

3.8 Data Analysis Process

Utilizing cutting-edge statistical tools, quantitative data are subjected to a thorough investigation. Calculations are made for descriptive statistics, such as means, medians, modes, percentages and standard deviation. Microsoft Excel and IBM SPSS software aid in the analytical process and guarantee a thorough examination of the collected data. Open-ended question analysis on thematic.

3.9 Ethical consideration

The study is integrated with ethical considerations. Participants are guaranteed 100% anonymity and confidentiality of their answers. Researcher took great care to get informed consent, which covers the objective of the research, the processes, and the ability to withdraw.

Extreme objectivity is maintained throughout the research process, and proactive steps are taken to reduce any possibility of researcher bias.

I've included a letter from the department that the dean and chairman signed. The letter of consent highlights the stakeholders' freedom to leave the study at any time without facing repercussions and describes the goals of the investigation as well as the anticipated length of involvement.

To protect participant privacy, the researcher does not gather any personally identifiable information from the survey, including names, email addresses, or contact information. The confidentiality of the responses is maintained throughout the study process by being securely saved and only accessible by the researcher. Participants are reassured that their answers will stay anonymous, strengthening the idea that their contributions are confidential.

3.10 Limitation of the study

There are obvious limitations to the study. However, this paper's specific focus on NSTU limits its wider applicability to other educational institutions. The amount of available information about NSTU's sustainability initiatives may impact on the breadth and accuracy of analysis.

It may be difficult for Universities in other countries or areas with different goals or problems to directly apply NSTU's contextual specificity elsewhere. However, the modifications necessary might be limited to what NSTU's unique conditions call for. The study may suffer from unintentional biases by its researchers and the investigation may be limited regarding how thorough it is due to time and resource constraints.

Table 1*Table of the methodology*

Data Source	Sampling Technique	Sample Size	Data Collection Technique	Tool
Students	Convenient Sampling	86		
Faculty			Survey	Survey Questionnaire
Staffs		05		

3.11 Conclusion

The NSTU’s sustainability initiative study was conducted by the researcher using quantitative research designs for find out valuable norm, attitude and knowledge among NSTU stakeholder. This survey employed cross-sectional approach; it focused on awareness, engagement, and challenges among stakeholders of NSTU; standard questionnaires were sent through Google forms. IBM SPSS software is used for data analysis along with thematic coding. It is drawn from local communities, teachers, staff and students which are conveniently selected to ensure diversity in representation. Ethical considerations necessitate participant confidentiality. However, these findings may not be applicable beyond their immediate context and should not be considered as such by those who read them. The main aim of this study format is to provide meaningful information about the sustainability landscape at NSTU. The results will inform campus improvement plans as well as contribute to wider discussions on higher education sustainability.

A graphic for Chapter 4. It features a light blue circle on the left containing the number '04'. To the right of the circle is a horizontal blue bar with rounded ends. The text 'CHAPTER FOUR' is written in a bold, black, serif font across the top of this bar. Below it, a smaller, narrower blue bar with rounded ends contains the text 'DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDING' in a bold, black, sans-serif font.

04

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDING

4.1 Introduction

A discussion is presented by this part researcher on the overall structure involving sustainable awareness, involvement, practices, communication channels, knowledge and views. Demographic data provides context for interpreting subsequent findings and highlights participants' heterogeneity. It examines sustainability awareness and involvement bringing out various points of view and levels of participation within the NSTU community. The study analyzes communication channels that expose preferences among participants to stress the importance of a sophisticated information developmental strategy.

From here on the chapter will discuss what is required to be done in terms of sustainability practices with an emphasis on encouraging positive involvement while pointing out deficiencies. This has been complemented by a critical element in which participants assess their sustainability knowledge leading to varied awareness levels hence recommending targeted pedagogical approaches. Assessment can facilitate changes that are aimed at improving reporting efficiency and incentives towards sustainability. As a result, this process provides valuable insights into attitudes as well as behavior patterns from people living within such communities. Overall, the NSTU community's thoughts on sustainability are better understood when all survey responses are reviewed, including open-ended ones – Sustainability reports versus non-reports, rewards and suggestions. Such qualitative information along with quantifiable numbers gives a full picture of what is going on in NSTU regarding sustainability at present.

To conclude this chapter, various aspects of how NSTU has embraced sustainable development shall be provided with a complicated view underlining tailor-made interventions and integrated approaches aimed at creating a campus culture that goes beyond merely recognizing SP into active participation. Findings from future studies will build on these findings to bridge gaps, raise awareness and promote SP among students in NSTU.

4.2 Demographic Information

The dataset has 67.7% males and another 32.3% females (*See: Table 1 and appendix-c; Figure- 4.1*). The age distribution is concentrated around the early twenties with noticeable representation at ages 18, 19, 23, and 24 (*See: Table 2*). Students are the majority (88.7%) while both faculty (5.2%) and staff (5.2%) are equally represented (*See: Table 1 and appendix-c; Figure- 4.2, 4.3*). The highest percentage (46.5) is in year four followed by years one to three. (*See: Table 2 and appendix-c; Figure- 4.4, 4.5*)

Table 2*Demographic Information*

Category	Frequency	Gender		Age		Study Year	
	(N=96)	(N=96)		(N=96)		(N=96)	
Student	89.6%	M	F	18-25	85.4%	1 st -2 nd	34.9%
Faculty	5.2%	67.7%	32.3%	25-40	12.3%	3 rd -4 th	59.3%
Staffs	5.2%			40+	2.3%	5 th	5.8%

Note: More demographic table and graph shown on appendix-C (figure: 4.1-4.6)

4.3 Analysis of the Study

4.3.0 NSTU's sustainability initiatives Awareness

The 7 level likert scale measured on Very Slightly Aware (1), Very Aware (2), Slightly Aware (3), Not Aware at All (4), Moderately Aware (5), I am Actively Involved (6), Extremely Aware (7) (*See:* More scale value Appendix- (ii) B).

The mean is 3.64, which is slightly above the middle of the scale Not Aware At All (4). That means most of the respondent was Not Aware at All in NSTU's sustainability initiative. This suggests that, on average, participants are somewhat aware of the issue (*See:* Table 3).

However, there is a large standard deviation of 4.86, which means that there is a wide range of responses. Some participants are very aware of the issue (scoring 7 on the scale), while others are not aware at all (scoring 1) (*See:* Table 3). The issue may be complex and difficult, respondent was not aware sustainability initiative, so some people may not be fully aware of it. Participants may come from different backgrounds and have different levels of knowledge about the sustainability awareness among NSTU stakeholders' issue.

Table 3*NSTU's sustainability initiatives Awareness*

Awareness Level	Participants
Very Slightly Aware (1)	14
Very Aware (2)	19
Slightly Aware (3)	29
Not Aware at All (4)	14
Moderately Aware (5)	7
I am Actively Involved (6)	7
Extremely Aware (7)	11
Mean	3.64
Standard Deviation	4.86

Note- Item 17; item list is on Appendix- (i) B

4.3.1 Sustainability Awareness and Participation in Sustainability Activities

A mean score of 2.6 implies that respondents generally feel somewhat informed about sustainability practices. This is evidenced by the standard deviation (1.1) (*See:* Table 4), which indicates a moderate level of variability between responses. It can therefore be concluded that while the average sentiment leans towards somewhat informed there exists a noticeable range within individual opinions.

The mean of 2.3 suggests that respondents find NSTU's sustainability initiatives to be somewhat effective, on average. A low standard deviation of 0.47 (*See:* Table 3) indicates that responses were given in a narrow range, which means that many respondents agreed with each other about the effectiveness of NSTU's sustainability initiatives. The mean of 2.03 suggests that respondents are somewhat interested in participating in future sustainability-related activities or programs at NSTU, on average. A low standard deviation of 0.2 indicates a relatively consistent level of interest among respondents with less variability in responses.

On average, the mean of 2.4 suggests that respondents occasionally review or access NSTU’s sustainability reports. The low standard deviation of 0.2 (*See: Table 3*) indicates a relatively consistent pattern of accessing sustainability reports with less variability in responses.

These analyses provide insights into respondent perceptions and attitudes towards sustainability practices and initiatives at NSTU. The low standard deviations for item 19, 20, and 21 suggest greater agreement among participants regarding these aspects when compared to item 18. The mean overall of 2.36 (*See: Table 3*) shows that the average attitude and perception of sustainability practices and initiatives at NSTU are somewhat positive.

The standard deviation of 0.52 (*See: Table 3*) indicates a moderate level of variability in overall responses. Although there is some level of agreement among respondents, there is also considerable diversity in their opinions leading to a moderate amount of variability in the general evaluation of awareness about sustainability and participation in sustainable activities at NSTU.

Table 4

Sustainability Awareness and Participation in Sustainability Activities

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation
Item 18	2.6	1.1
Item 19	2.3	0.4
Item 20	2	0.2
Item 21	2.4	0.2
Overall	2.3	0.5

Note: 5 Scale Value- Very Ineffective (1), Ineffective (2), Neutral (3), Effective (4), Very Effective (5), more 5 scale value added in appendix B(ii)

4.3.2 Communication Channels

According to an analysis of the preferred channels of communication for NSTU's sustainability projects, social media platforms—specifically Facebook, X, and LinkedIn—are

preferred by 44.3% of participants. With a 14.4% dependability rate, the university website is the second most frequently chosen medium. Notably, 8.2% of participants selected "Other," suggesting that there are other channels that aren't on the list (*See: Figure 1*).

The information highlights a clear preference for digital media, which is consistent with current communication patterns. The variety of carefully chosen channel combinations—which include social media, university websites, campus announcements/posters, and word-of-mouth—highlights the significance of utilizing a multimodal communication approach. The university's social media presence should be enhanced, the website should be updated frequently and made user-friendly, channels under the "Other" category should be explored and optimized, and an integrated communication plan should be put in place.

It is recommended that a feedback mechanism be established in order to assess the efficacy of communication channels and make appropriate modifications in order to improve knowledge and engagement in sustainability activities throughout NSTU.

Figure 1

Receive information about NSTU's sustainability initiatives

4.3.3 Sustainability Practices

4.3.3.1 Recycling

Mean: 3.4, Standard Deviation: 1.1. The mean score suggests a moderate level (sometimes) participant maintained recycling in sometimes, and the low standard deviation indicates relatively low variability among responses (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.2 Conserving Energy

Mean: 3.53, Standard Deviation: 1.21. Similar to Item 1, the mean is moderate level (sometimes) participant maintained conserving energy in sometimes, and the standard deviation is relatively low, indicating consistent responses (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.3 Reducing Waste of Water

Mean: 3.75, Standard Deviation: 1.2. The mean score is higher, indicating a relatively positive response (often) on average. Participant maintained reducing waste of water in often. The standard deviation is moderate, suggesting some variability in responses (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.4 Reducing Waste of Energy

Mean: 3.69, Standard Deviation: 1.16, Similar to Item 3, a higher mean with a low standard deviation suggests a generally positive response with less variability (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.5 Reducing Polythene Uses (Plastic)

Mean: 3.31, Standard Deviation: 1.3. The mean is moderate(sometimes) participant maintained reducing polythene and plastic uses sometimes, but the higher standard deviation implies more variability in responses compared to previous items (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.6 Attending Tree-Plantation Programs

Mean: 3.25, Standard Deviation: 1.47. The mean is relatively moderate (sometimes) participant attending tree plantation programs sometimes and the higher standard deviation indicates greater variability in responses, suggesting mixed opinions (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.7 Maintained Waste Management

Mean: 3.38, Standard Deviation: 1.51, Similar to Item 6, the mean is moderate(sometimes) participant maintaining waste management sometimes, but the high standard deviation suggests diverse responses and less consensus (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.8 Composting

Mean: 3.16, Standard Deviation: 1.31. The mean is slightly moderate (sometimes) participant maintaining composting sometimes, and the standard deviation is relatively high, indicating more variability and potentially conflicting opinions (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.9 Participating in Eco-Friendly Events

Mean: 3.21, Standard Deviation: 1.21. The mean is moderate (sometimes) participant maintaining participating eco-friendly event sometimes, and the standard deviation is relatively low, suggesting a more consistent response pattern (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.10 Supporting Local and Sustainable Food Options

Mean: 3.54 Standard Deviation: 1.23, The mean is moderate (sometimes) participant maintaining supporting local and sustainable food option sometimes, and the standard deviation is relatively low, indicating a consistent, moderately positive response (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.11 Using Reusable Water Bottles and Containers

Mean: 3.4, Standard Deviation: 1.22. The mean is moderate (sometimes) participant using reusable water bottles and containers sometimes, and the standard deviation is relatively low, indicating a consistent response pattern (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.12 Encouraging SP among Peers/Students

Mean: 3.31, Standard Deviation: 1.19. The mean is moderate (sometimes) participant encouraging SP among peers/ student sometimes, and the standard deviation is relatively low, suggesting a more consistent response pattern (*See: Table 5*).

4.3.3.13 Participating in Clean-Up and Beautification Efforts

Mean: 3.4, Standard Deviation: 1.18. Similar to Item 11, the mean is moderate (sometimes) (*See: Table 5*) participant encouraging SP among peers/ student sometimes, and the standard deviation is relatively low, indicating a consistent response pattern

Across all categories, the mean overall was about 3.41 (*See: Table 5*). This implies that participants usually have a moderate level of agreement with respect to environmental behaviors and practices.

Higher means for categories like "Reducing Waste of Water" and "Conserving Energy" show comparatively more agreement or adherence to the behaviors described within these groups.

Lower means for categories like “Participating in Eco-friendly Events” and “Supporting Local and Sustainable Food Options” indicate less concordance or less frequent involvement in these particular behaviors.

Table 5

Sustainability Practices

Category	Mean	Standard Deviation
Item 1	3.42	1.17
Item 2	3.53	1.21
Item 3	3.75	1.2
Item 4	3.69	1.16
Item 5	3.31	1.3
Item 6	3.25	1.47
Item 7	3.38	1.51
Item 8	3.16	1.31
Item 9	3.21	1.21
Item 10	3.54	1.23
Item 11	3.4	1.22
Item 12	3.31	1.19
Item 13	3.4	1.18
Overall	3.411	1.26

Note: Scale value 1= never, 2= rarely, 3=sometimes, 4= often, 5= always

4.3.4.1 Analysis of Standard Deviation

On the whole, the standard deviation is about 1.26, which represents how responses vary across all categories.

Lower standard deviations in some categories like "Recycling" and "Reducing Waste of Energy" show that opinions or behaviors are more consistent within these areas as they tend to cluster around the mean.

Higher standard deviations in categories such as "Maintained Waste Management" and "Using Reusable Water Bottles and Containers" imply a wider range of responses, meaning that participants have a greater diversity of ideas and actions in relation to these issues.

4.3.4.2 Overall Summary

The results reveal mostly positive attitudes towards conducting environmentally friendly activities among respondents.

It may be necessary to probe into those domains where means are lower or there is greater variation so as to identify what accounts for different answers given by individuals taking part in the research.

When interpreting these findings, one should put each category into context and consider specific behaviors being analyzed.

4.3.4 Sustainability Knowledge

The self-assessment of sustainability knowledge by participants at NSTU was analyzed, and the results show a wide range of reported awareness levels. Regarding their understanding of sustainability, a sizable percentage (29.9%) regard themselves as "Somewhat Informed," signifying a substantial degree of awareness, whereas 27.8% feel "Neutral" about it (*See: Figure 2*).

Notably, 17.5% of respondents felt "Very Informed," indicating that a sizable fraction of respondents possess a high degree of knowledge. On the other hand, 16.5% (*See: Figure 2*) acknowledge that they feel "Very Uninformed," demonstrating a consciousness of their ignorance. This variant points to the necessity of specialized educational initiatives with an emphasis on fundamental

Sustainability ideas to fill up particular knowledge gaps. It is advised that NSTU improve its understanding of sustainability by the following means: making information easily available,

encouraging candid discussions, carrying out regular evaluations, and recognizing moments of greater consciousness.

Through these initiatives, the campus community hopes to become actively involved in advocating and putting SP into practice, in addition to being aware of them.

Figure 2

Sustainability Knowledge

4.3.5 Reporting, Effectiveness and Incentives for Sustainable Behavior

The efficiency of NSTU's sustainability programs, participants' familiarity with sustainability reports, and their attitudes toward incentives for sustainable conduct were all analyzed in order to gain important insights into the attitudes and behaviors of the campus community. The report shows a generally positive opinion of sustainability programs, with 51.5% showing interest in future activities and 40.2% (See: Figure 3) finding them effective. Addressing concerns about a lack of information and boosting participation in seminars or training, however, are areas that still need effort.

There is a clear lack of knowledge with sustainability reports; 46.4% of participants said they were unaware (See: Figure 3) of NSTU's sustainability reports. Increased involvement may result from improving communication, expanding the availability of information, and incorporating reporting into the academic program.

When it comes to rewards for sustainable behavior, the majority (61.5%) is more likely to participate (See: Figure 3) in SP if they receive scholarships, which are found to be the most

successful kind of reward. Moreover, job advancement and recognition were brought up, demonstrating the ability of a variety of incentives to encourage sustainable conduct.

Figure 3

Sustainable Campus Pulse: NSTU Insights

4.3.6 Challenges of implementing sustainability

4.3.6.1 Sustainability Challenges

It was also observed that among responses to open-ended survey questions regarding sustainability challenges at NSTU, a wide variety of perspectives emerged, with three primary themes being identified as top priorities for the campus community.

4.3.6.1.1 Environmental Concerns

Firstly, environmental concerns like tree planting, water pollution and plastic usage are clearly indicated. It implies that there has been common knowledge about the importance of conserving or enhancing the environment within the university grounds.

4.3.6.1.2 Infrastructure Needs

Secondly, infrastructure needs like classroom facilities, games facilities and overall campus development were mentioned in general terms. This suggests a realization that SP encompass more than just ecological aspects but also include physical structures/facilities which support students' life on campus.

4.3.6.1.3 Waste Management

The third main issue was waste management. Respondents expressed concern over minimizing plastic use, cleaning up after social events, and raising awareness about waste management methods. These changes indicate the necessity of more efficient and long-lived procedures for disposing trash on campus.

In addition to these dominant themes, they made some recommendations and gave suggestions that are helpful in dealing with sustainability problems. These comprise; creating awareness and interest in sustainability programs amongst people, improving eco-friendly infrastructures, increasing energy efficiency as well as working together with community-based organizations that work to clean up the environment.

4.3.6.2 Reasons for not participating in sustainability activities

Some participants mentioned several reasons why they did not take part in NSTU's efforts aimed at promoting sustainability. Some of them include lack of interest, ignorance about the available initiatives, time constraints, being new to university or a foreigner, few opportunities for involvement, and absence of an active group or team focused on sustainability. If these challenges are addressed, NSTU will be able to boost participation rates and ultimately nurture an inclusive sustainability culture. In conclusion, individuals expressed their regret at not taking part in sustainability activities-

- Lack of interest
- Lack of information
- Time constraints
- Newcomer/Not aware of university protocols
- Lack of opportunity
- Lack of active association or team

4.3.6.3 Incentives or Rewards to Motivating Sustainable Behavior

The respondents have different thoughts on how NSTU can motivate its people towards sustainable actions. These motivational factors include.

Knowing this will help NSTU understand what incentives acceptable and which ones are not to its different communities. Thus, there is a need for the university to create incentive programs that will meet the needs of the diverse campus community.

Table 6*Awareness programs sustainability activities*

Awareness programs	Rewards
Sustainability Practices	Scholarship, Recognition, Promotion, Financial help
Attending Campaigns	Social recognition, Free plants, Discounts, Public appreciation
Proper information and techniques	Public appreciation

4.3.6.4 Ways to involve more students, faculty, and staff in sustainability efforts

In other words, participants want more inclusion in the sustainability effort at NSTU from various populations. In addition, NSTU needs multiple approaches to plan educational activities, induce mandatory participation as well as link with other agencies.

Table 7*Ways to stakeholders involve sustainability*

Initiative	Encouragement
Awareness programs	Seminars, Campaigns, Proper information and techniques
Encouragement	Promotions, Compulsory participation for every department
Involvement	Activists, Social organizations
Resources	Instruments, Facilities

Therefore, by understanding and appreciating these diverse points of view, NSTU could develop a holistic framework that would encompass all aspects of education and empowerment in order advance sustainable development within its walls.

4.3.6.5 Suggestions for NSTU's Sustainability Initiatives:

Respondents suggested and comment for improving NSTU sustainability initiative, Impact and challenge

- Focus on building a sustainable and eco-friendly campus
- Improve transport, residential facilities, and food facilities
- Increase awareness through social media
- Reward students for their work in sustainability programs
- Engage all individuals related to the campus
- Plant more trees
- Provide quality food in the canteen
- Implement eco-friendly infrastructure
- Prioritize the cleanliness of the campus
- Encourage through different activities
- Involve more employees in sustainability initiatives
- Conduct more awareness programs
- Have a well-motivated plan

4.4 Finding

Key Findings of NSTU Sustainability Initiatives Survey-

4.4.1 Fragmented understanding and commitment to sustainability

Lack of awareness and participation vary across different groups, highlighting the need for targeted educational campaigns and engagement strategies tailored to diverse audiences.

4.4.2 Positive attitude towards sustainability programs

Most people are looking forward to what will come ahead and find them effective, indicating a positive foundation for building comprehensive sustainability initiatives that align with community values.

4.4.3 Lack of knowledge about sustainability reports

Stakeholders' unawareness of NSTU's reports emphasizes the importance of transparent communication channels and the need for disseminating information effectively to keep all relevant parties informed.

4.4.4 Diverse reasons for low participation

Lack of awareness, time constraints, and lack of opportunity underscore the necessity for multifaceted approaches, including educational outreach, flexible participation options, and creating accessible avenues for involvement.

4.4.5 Opportunities to improve

Enhancing dialogue, diversifying incentives, and addressing specific challenges to increase participation offer a roadmap for strengthening sustainability initiatives and fostering a culture of shared responsibility within the NSTU community.

4.4.6 Challenges remain

Diverse needs, information gaps filling, and ingrained behavior changes are some of the ways in which NSTU can develop a strong basis for sustainability, indicating the necessity for ongoing efforts and a holistic approach to overcome existing hurdles.

4.4.7 Potential to contribute to Bangladesh's sustainability goals

NSTU has a good foundation for sustainability, but some places need to address challenges and capitalize on opportunities to become a leading example, showcasing the university's potential to play a pivotal role in Bangladesh's broader sustainability agenda.

4.4.8 Promoting Sustainability

Implementing sustainable practices not only helps protect the environment but also contributes to long-term socio-economic well-being, emphasizing the interconnectedness of environmental and societal health.

4.4.9 Providing incentives

Sustainable initiatives can be promoted through tangible rewards and recognition, creating a culture of environmental accountability among individuals and organizations involved, fostering a sense of shared responsibility.

4.4.10 Increasing Facilities

Moreover, enhancing transportation as well as residential options and subsidizing food prices will improve campus life conditions while conforming to sustainable development goals, thereby creating an eco-friendly, student-friendly environment that aligns with global sustainability targets.

4.4.11 Regular Checking for Good Governance

A check and balance system for purposes of transparency and accountability must be put in place, along with effective implementation of e-governance, to streamline administrative processes for efficiency and uphold principles of good governance.

4.4.12 Proper Implementation of Sustainability Curricula

Ensuring that sustainability-focused curricula are properly integrated enables students to acquire knowledge and skills for dealing with environmental problems, thereby nurturing a generation that upholds sustainable practices and contributes to a more environmentally conscious society.

4.5 Conclusion

NSTU has a fragmented society with little uniformity or commonness in its understanding, commitment and practices toward sustainability when approached holistically. These demographic tendencies reinforce how important individualized responses are. Although

there have been some improvements including heightened composting awareness and increased number of sustainability programs taking place but poor participation plus lack of knowledge still remain evident.

Therefore, suggestions below are made from this study on what approach should be followed considering target audience's perceived needs through digital media is discussed by means of strategic communication. This implies that there should be another form of teaching specifically designed to target some areas where their learners lack sufficient information. Sustainability programs have favorable opinions, which indicate that they could be improved upon by enhancing participation rates, filling information gaps and diversifying incentives.

The open-ended responses reveal rich qualitative data on what is most important in terms of waste management, infrastructure needs and environmental concerns. The suggestions include digitalizing communication, eliminating barriers to participation as well as changing rewards depending on the community's choice.

Finally, this analysis is a guide for creating an NSTU campus that is diverse, active and sustainable. By addressing identified challenges and involving the community point of view, this university will steer future undertakings and foster a culture of carefulness in citizenship as regards the environment.

A graphic for a chapter title. It features a light blue circular button with a drop shadow on the left, containing the number '05'. To its right is a horizontal blue bar with rounded ends, containing the text 'CHAPTER FIVE' and 'CONCLUSION' stacked vertically.

05

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION

5.1 Introduction

The sustainability Initiative at NSTU, researcher focus sharpens on distilling key insights and shaping a pragmatic roadmap for the future. The preceding chapters have unraveled the intricacies of awareness, participation, and practices within the university community. This final chapter is our compass, guiding us through a concise synthesis of findings and implications. We revisit our study objectives, highlighting successes and areas for improvement. The aim is not just to summarize but to distill actionable insights that can propel NSTU toward a more sustainable future.

Join us in this brief yet impactful exploration as we navigate sustainable pathways at NSTU, translating data into actionable strategies for a more environmentally conscious and engaged campus community.

5.2 Discussion of the findings

Male respondents constitute the highest proportion of NSTU participants-67.7%, mostly students (88.7%) and mainly fourth-year ones (46.5%). According to Hunter et al. (2023), this implies that sustainability initiatives must be customized to suit various university community cohorts.

Generally, respondents show moderate levels of awareness on NSTU's sustainability initiatives; average level of awareness was 3.64 which is slightly above the midpoint showing some sort of awareness; a wide standard deviation of 4.86 indicates that there were different responses given by different people hence varying levels of awareness among the respondents (Devine & Ash, 2022). On the whole, participants feel somewhat informed about practices in regard to sustainability (mean = 2.6). They view NSTU's sustainability initiatives as somewhat effective (mean = 2.3).

On average, respondents have moderate interest in participating in future activities associated with sustainability (mean = 2). Participants usually go through or access occasionally NSTU's sustainability reports (mean = 2.4). 44.3% of participants prefer social media platforms, particularly Facebook, X, and LinkedIn for communication. (Dependability rate: 14.4%). Hence the recommendation to improve the university website's social media presence and optimize communication channels (Shields & Peruta, 2019).

Participants generally express positive attitudes towards environmentally friendly behavior with a mean score of approximately 3.41 across all categories indicating a moderate level of

agreement with respect to sustainability practices. Higher means in some categories like “Reducing Waste of Water” and “Conserving Energy” show greater agreement or adherence (Hansmann & Binder, 2020).

Many respondents had moderate levels of sustainability knowledge while others had low scores while others high scores in sustainability knowledge. Efforts towards improving understanding include making information easily available, encouraging discussions as well as conducting regular evaluations (Fallah Shayan et al., 2022).

Overall there were generally positive opinions concerning sustainability programs; however, there was also interest in future activities (51.5%) and perceived effectiveness (40.2%). The absence of knowledge about the sustainability reports (46.4 percent) implies that communication and better integration into academic programs is needed (Clark et al., 2021). Scholarships have been identified as the most successful incentive for sustainable behaviour (61.5%) (Huber et al., 2017). Some of the Sustainability challenges include concerns on environmental, infrastructure needs and waste management. Recommendations include creating awareness, improving eco-friendly infrastructure and working closely with CBOs (Debnath et al., 2023). Reasons for not participating are lack of interest, lack of information, time constraints, no active groups or teams. By addressing these challenges participation rates may increase hence fostering inclusive sustainability culture (Mccowan et al., 2021).

The participants want to be involved in the sustainability efforts more. Recommendations include awareness programs, involvement of activists and provision of resources (Burlison et al., 2023). On building a sustainable campus, improving facilities increasing awareness through social media platforms and implementation of eco- friendly infrastructures as suggested by respondents (Mohammadi et al., 2023).

NSTU society is fragmented on sustainability with different perceptions, commitments, and acts. To enhance sustainability programs, it is important to improve participation rates, fill information gaps and diversify incentives. In order to foster a sustainable and inclusive campus culture in the future, the author suggests addressing these challenges and including community perspectives (Zheng et al., 2021).

5.3 Recommendations

Here are recommendations based on the findings-

5.3.1 Communication Strategy

Strengthen social media presence, particularly on Facebook, X, and LinkedIn.

Optimize the university website for user-friendliness.

Implement an integrated communication strategy.

5.3.2 Awareness and Education

Conduct targeted awareness campaigns across departments.

Develop educational initiatives for foundational sustainability concepts.

Provide accessible resources and facilitate open dialogues.

5.3.3 Inclusive Participation:

Create diverse engagement opportunities.

Establish a feedback mechanism for communication effectiveness.

Involve more students, faculty, and staff through tailored initiatives.

5.3.4 Sustainable Practices:

Promote behaviors with lower participation rates (recycling, energy conservation).

Organize eco-friendly events, tree-plantation programs, and clean-up efforts.

5.3.5 Incentives for Sustainable Behavior

Develop diverse incentives, including scholarships, recognition, and discounts.

5.3.6 Addressing Challenges

Prioritize environmental concerns, infrastructure needs, and waste management.

Collaborate with external organizations for improved waste management.

5.3.7 Continuous Improvement

Regular surveys and feedback mechanisms help to gauge effectiveness.

Improve strategies based on answers that change with time.

5.3.8 Overcoming Resource Limitations

To augment its resources for sustainability initiatives engage partnerships with NSTU's partnering civil society organizations, local government units as well as Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs).

Overcoming financial constraints can be done by finding alternative financing options such as grants or sponsorships or collaborations for supporting long-term sustainability goals.

5.3.9 Improving Accessibility to Sustainability Reports

People should be able to easily locate NSTU's sustainability reports or disclosures.

Different channels of communication such as social media, websites and notice boards within the campus should regularly provide information about it.

Conducting workshops or training programs that teach stakeholders how to use sustainability reports.

These are some brief suggestions that can make NSTU have a better and more sustainable campus life.

5.4 Conclusion

The sustainability Initiative at NSTU, researcher focus sharpens on distilling key insights and shaping a pragmatic roadmap for the future. The preceding chapters have unraveled the intricacies of awareness, participation. While there are some commendable sustainable practices, others require improvements, particularly regarding energy conservation. Varied levels of self-assessed knowledge about sustainability signify the significance of specific educational activities. Positive attitudes towards sustainability initiatives provide an avenue for improvements with issues raised such as addressing information gaps and diversifying incentives.

To sum up, this paper is an avenue that will assist to have a more inclusive, committed and sustainable direction at NSTU. The findings present possible lines for future research and strategic actions illustrating how changeable a sustainable development could be within an education institution.

In conclusion, this paper provides guidance towards developing a more inclusive, engaged and sustainable campus at NSTU. To understand the current trends in sustainability at universities, we must look at how they are approaching this topic and what actions they are taking.

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APPENDIX-A

Evaluating the Impact and Challenges of Campus Sustainability Initiatives at Noakhali
Science and Technology University

Tool's name: Survey Questionnaire

Campus Sustainability Initiatives at Noakhali Science and Technology University

Welcome to the "Evaluating the Impact and Challenges of CS Initiatives" Survey! To achieve this, I want to invite the Noakhali Science and Technology University community, including all its members such as students, faculty members, staff, and administrators etc., to take part in this survey.

Campus Sustainability

Sustainability is the idea of managing resources and running activities that can fulfill the needs of today without compromising the capacity of future generations to meet theirs. It also means that there is a balance between economic development, environmental preservation, and social equity for present as well as future generations. In relation to a Universities/university setting, sustainability initiatives aim towards enhancing environmental responsibility and social justice by making effective campus practices operational policy changes.

Demographic Information

Thank you very much for participating in our survey. The information provided here will be used solely for research purposes and will be treated confidentially. Your responses will help us gain valuable insights into the backgrounds and experiences of our participants. Thank you for providing us with this important information.

1. Name (Optional)
2. What is your gender?
3. Department/Faculty
4. Position (e.g., Student, Teacher, Staff)
5. What department are you currently studying?

Survey Questionnaire			
Items		Coding Categories	Code No.
Sustainability Awareness¹	6. How aware are you of NSTU's sustainability initiatives?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1 - Not Aware at All ▪ 2 - Very Slightly Aware ▪ 3 - Slightly Aware ▪ 4 - Moderately Aware ▪ 5 - Very Aware ▪ 6 - Extremely Aware ▪ 7 - I am Actively Involved 	
	7. Which specific sustainability initiatives or programs at NSTU are you aware of?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1 – Tree Plantation ▪ 2 - research, teaching, and practices ▪ 3 - improved academic infrastructures ▪ 4 – Mental Health ▪ 5 – Others [....] 	
Participation in Sustainability Activities²	8. Have you actively participated in any sustainability programme?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Never (1) ▪ Rarely (2) ▪ Sometimes (3) ▪ Often (4) ▪ Always (5) 	
	9. If you have not participated in sustainability activities, please share the reasons for not being involved (e.g., lack of information, lack of interest, time constraints).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ lack of information (1) ▪ lack of interest (2) ▪ time constraints (3) ▪ Other [.....] (4) 	

¹ Adopted from (Msengi et al., 2019)

² Adopted from (Pauw et al., 2015)

Communication Channels³	10. How do you typically receive information about NSTU's sustainability initiatives? (Select all that apply)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ University website(1) ▪ University email newsletters(2) ▪ Social media (3) ▪ Notices/posters on campus(4) ▪ Word of mouth (5) ▪ from colleagues or peers (6) ▪ Other (please specify) 	
Sustainability Practices⁴	A. Recycling B. Conserving Energy C. Reducing Waste Of Water D. Reducing Waste Of Energy E. Reducing Polythene F. Attending Tree-Plantation G. Maintained Waste Management H. Participating in Eco-Friendly I. Supporting Local And Sustainable J. Using Reusable Water Bottles and Containers K. Encouraging Sustainable L. Practices Among Peers/Students M. Participating In Clean-Up And N. Beautification Efforts O. Adopting Energy-Efficient P. Appliances And Lighting Q. Food Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Never (1) ▪ Rarely (2) ▪ Sometimes (3) ▪ Often (4) ▪ Always (5) 	
Sustainability Knowledge⁵	12. Well-informed do you feel about sustainability practices and their importance?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Very Uninformed (1) ▪ Somewhat Uninformed (2) ▪ Neutral(3) ▪ Somewhat Informed (4) ▪ Very Informed(5) 	

³ Modified in local context, adopted from (*Sustainability awareness survey 2019*, N.D)

⁴ Modified in local context, adopted from (*Sustainability awareness survey 2019*, N.D)

⁵ Adopted from (Bhowmik et al., 2017)

Sustainability Initiatives Effectiveness⁶	13. How effective do you believe NSTU's sustainability initiatives are in addressing environmental and sustainability issues on campus?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Never (1) ▪ Rarely (2) ▪ Sometimes (3) ▪ Often (4) ▪ Always (5) 	
	14. How interested would you be in participating in future sustainability-related activities or programs at NSTU?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Never (1) ▪ Rarely (2) ▪ Sometimes (3) ▪ Often (4) ▪ Always (5) 	
	15. Have you ever participated in sustainability-related training or workshops organized by NSTU?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Never (1) ▪ Rarely (2) ▪ Sometimes (3) ▪ Often (4) ▪ Always (5) 	
	16. If you have not participated in sustainability training or workshops, what would encourage you to do so? (e.g., more information, convenient timing)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Very Ineffective (1) ▪ Ineffective (2) ▪ Neutral (3) ▪ Effective (4) ▪ Very Effective (5) 	
Sustainability Reporting⁷	17. Are you familiar with NSTU's sustainability reports or disclosures that detail its environmental and social performance?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Yes (1) ▪ No(2) ▪ May Be (3) 	
	18. How often do you review or access NSTU's sustainability reports, if at all?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Never (1) ▪ Rarely (2) ▪ Sometimes (3) ▪ Often (4) ▪ Always (5) 	

⁶ Adopted from (Kioupi & Voulvoulis, 2019)

⁷ Adopted from (Bhowmik et al., 2017)

Incentives for Sustainable Behavior ⁸	19. Would you be more inclined to engage in SP on campus if NSTU offered incentives or rewards for doing so?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Discounts-1 ▪ scholarship-2 ▪ promotion-3 ▪ recognition-4 	
	20. What types of incentives or rewards do you believe would be most effective in motivating sustainable behavior among NSTU stakeholders?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Text box 	
Sustainability Challenges ^{9,10}	21. In your opinion, what are the top three sustainability challenges NSTU should prioritize addressing in the near future?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Textbox 	
	22. How do you think NSTU can involve more students, faculty, and staff in sustainability efforts, even if they are currently less engaged?		
Suggestions and Comments	23. Please provide any additional comments, suggestions, or ideas you may have regarding NSTU's sustainability initiatives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Textbox 	

⁸ Adopted from (Lin & Chiu, 2023)

⁹ Modified local context and adopted from (Hasan et al., 2023)

¹⁰ Adopted from (Bhowmik et al., 2017)

APPENDIX-B

Study Title: Evaluating the Impact and Challenges of Campus Sustainability Initiatives at Noakhali Science and Technology University

(I) ITEM NUMBER AND NAME

Item No.	Item Name
1	Recycling
2	Conserving Energy
3	Reducing Waste of Water
4	Reducing Waste of Energy
5	Reducing Polythene Uses (Plastic)
6	Attending Tree-plantation Programme
7	Maintained Waste Management
8	Participating in Eco-friendly Events
9	Supporting Local and Sustainable Food Options
10	Using Reusable Water Bottles and Containers
11	Encouraging Sustainable Practices Among Peers/students
12	Participating in Clean-up and Beautification Efforts
13	Adopting Energy-Efficient Appliances and Lighting
14	Sustainability practices incentive
15	Sustainability related report/disclosure
16	Sustainability related training
17	NSTU's sustainability initiatives Awareness
18	Sustainability awareness
19	NSTU's sustainability impact
20	Stakeholder Future engagement
21	NSTU's sustainability report accessibility

(II) SCALE VALUE

Sustainability Awareness

- 1 - Not Aware at All
- 2 - Very Slightly Aware
- 3 - Slightly Aware
- 4 - Moderately Aware
- 5 - Very Aware
- 6 - Extremely Aware
- 7 - I am Actively Involved

Sustainability Practices, Sustainability Reporting

- Never (1)
- Rarely (2)
- Sometimes (3)
- Often (4)
- Always (5)

Sustainability Initiatives Effectiveness

- Very Ineffective (1)
- Ineffective (2)
- Neutral (3)
- Effective (4)
- Very Effective (5)

Sustainability Knowledge

- Very Uninformed (1)
- Somewhat Uninformed (2)
- Neutral(3)
- Somewhat Informed (4)
- Very Informed(5)

APPENDIX-C

Study Title: Evaluating the Impact and Challenges of Campus Sustainability Initiatives at Noakhali Science and Technology University

Additional Chart, Graph and Histogram

Figure 4.1

Demographic Information

1. What is your gender?

96 responses

Figure 4.2

Demographic Information

3. What is your position at NSTU?

96 responses

Figure 4.3

Demographic Information

5. What department are you currently studying?

86 responses

Figure 4.4

Demographic Information

4. How many years of teaching experience do you have at NSTU?

5 responses

Figure 4.5

Demographic Information

4. How many years of experience do you have at NSTU?

5 responses

Figure 4.6

Demographic Information

5. What department are you currently teaching?

5 responses

Figure 4.7

Demographic Information

5. In which area of NSTU are you employed?

5 responses

Figure 5

Aware of sustainability Initiative

6. How aware are you of NSTU's sustainability initiatives?

96 responses

Figure 6

Training

15. Have you ever participated in sustainability-related training or workshops organized by NSTU?

96 responses

Figure 7

Reports/ Disclosures

17. Are you familiar with NSTU's sustainability reports or disclosures that detail its environmental and social performance?

96 responses

Figure 8

Sustainability report

18.How often do you review or access NSTU's sustainability reports, if at all?

96 responses

Figure 9

Sustainability Practices Incentive

19.Would you be more inclined to engage in sustainable practices on campus if NSTU offered incentives or rewards for doing so? (e.g., discounts, scholarship,promotion, recognition)

96 responses

